

SUPPORTING INFORMATION (SI)

Severe environmental conditions create severe conflicts: A novel ecological pathway to extreme coyote attacks on humans.

Table S1. Predictions generated from two hypotheses related to coyote-human conflict.

Parameter	Limited Resource Hypothesis	Anthropogenic Resource Hypothesis
Home Range Size	Large	Small
Habitat Selection	Avoidance of areas used by humans	Selection for areas used by humans
Activity	Temporal avoidance of periods of high human activity	Temporal shift toward periods of high human activity
Diet Composition	Limited or no use of human foods	High use of human foods
Diet Variation (Intra- and Inter-Individual)	Low and focused on few natural food items	High or if low focused on human foods

Table S2. Mean weight (kg) and associated standard deviation (SD) of coyotes grouped by sex and age class captured in Cape Breton Highlands National Park, 2010-2013.

Sex	Age	n	Mean	SD
Female	Adult	2	12.2	0.7
	Juvenile	2	7.5	1.5
Male	Adult	15	16.1	1.9
	Juvenile	4	6.9	1.3

Table S3. Individual metadata and mean vibrissae carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) isotope values and associated standard deviation (SD) for individual coyotes; n denotes the sample size of whisker segments analyzed for each individual.

Sample ID	Sex	Age	Capture Date	Tag ID	n	Mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ SD	Mean $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ SD
CBH-017	Female	Adult	10/15/12	CH-13	15	-19.8	1.0	9.1	1.2
CBH-020	Female	Adult	9/30/12	N/A	21	-20.5	1.0	9.0	1.0
CBH-030	Female	Juvenile	9/1/10	X32336-10	24	-21.8	1.4	8.5	1.8
CBH-036	Male	Adult	8/30/11	N/A	12	-21.5	1.2	6.9	2.2
CBH-035	Male	Juvenile	7/26/11	X20016-11-2	13	-22.8	1.2	3.9	0.8
CBH-013	Female	Adult	10/14/12	CH-11	17	-22.9	0.5	3.8	0.5
CBH-01	Male	Adult	10/27/11	CH-01	15	-22.7	0.5	4.2	0.5
CBH-033	Female	Juvenile	10/14/11	X27905-11	22	-22.6	0.9	5.0	1.7
CBH-019	Male	Adult	11/10/12	CH-17	17	-23.0	0.3	3.7	0.4
CBH-06	Male	Adult	11/19/11	CH-06	15	-22.7	1.3	4.3	2.3
CBH-015	Female	Adult	10/24/12	CH-14	11	-22.9	0.3	4.4	0.5
CBH-05	Male	Adult	11/13/11	CH-05	14	-23.1	0.2	4.0	0.3
CBH-032	Female	Juvenile	10/14/11	X27906-11	12	-22.7	1.5	4.6	2.1
CBH-028	Female	Adult	5/8/12	N/A	23	-23.2	0.3	4.1	0.6
CBH-026	Female	Adult	N/A	X30740-09	22	-23.3	0.4	4.0	0.3
CBH-011	Female	Adult	8/20/12	CH-09	14	-23.2	0.4	4.3	0.5
CBH-04	Female	Juvenile	11/11/11	CH-04	13	-22.2	1.5	4.9	2.3
CBH-021	Male	Adult	11/10/12	CH-18	16	-23.1	0.2	4.6	0.5
CBH-014	Male	Juvenile	10/18/12	CH-12	21	-23.0	0.3	4.8	0.6
CBH-018	Female	Adult	11/5/12	N/A	15	-22.7	0.2	5.1	0.4
CBH-025	Male	Adult	N/A	X31393-09	7	-23.1	0.4	4.2	0.5
CBH-016	Female	Juvenile	11/7/12	CH-16	16	-23.2	0.3	4.7	0.6
CBH-037	Male	Adult	N/A	X22871-10	13	-23.4	0.2	3.7	0.2
CBH-024	Female	Juvenile	11/11/09	X33354-09	16	-23.4	0.3	4.3	0.6
CBH-029	Female	Adult	7/6/12	N/A	6	-22.9	0.1	4.6	0.3
CBH-031	Female	Juvenile	12/1/10	X32335-10	23	-23.5	0.3	3.4	0.8
CBH-023	Male	Juvenile	11/11/09	X33904-09	18	-23.5	0.4	4.3	0.3
CBH-034	Female	Juvenile	7/26/11	X20016-11-1	10	-23.5	0.5	3.6	0.4
CBH-012	Male	Juvenile	10/13/12	CH-10	23	-23.3	0.4	4.1	1.7
CBH-07	Male	Adult	12/27/11	CH-03	11	-22.9	0.4	6.2	0.6
CBH-09	Male	Adult	6/26/12	CH-07	5	-21.9	0.8	6.5	0.6
CBH-027	Male	Adult	N/A	X33906-09	41	-23.7	0.3	7.0	0.7

Table S4. Mean hair carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) isotope values and associated standard deviation (SD) for potential prey and humans collected from Cape Breton National Park and adjacent communities; n denotes the sample size of each group.

Common Name	Species	n	Mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ SD	Mean $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ SD
Deer	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	20	-26.1	0.4	4.4	1.1
Moose	<i>Alces americanus</i>	21	-25.2	1.4	1.4	1.5
Snowshoe Hare	<i>Lepus americanus</i>	17	-26.5	1.1	1.6	1.7
Small Mammals	<i>Myodes gapperi</i> / <i>Sorex spp.</i>	76	-23.7	1.0	6.0	1.9
Humans	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	20	-18.7	0.6	9.1	0.6

Table S5. Mean contributions (%) and associated standard deviation (SD) of four natural prey types to the diet of individual coyotes (n=28) based on an isotope mixing model. Note that the four individuals whose whisker isotope profiles clearly show they switched between natural and anthropogenic resources (Fig. 3B) were not included in the mixing model analysis because no isotope data were available for local human foods.

Sample ID	Moose	SD	White-Tailed Deer	SD	Snowshoe Hare	SD	Small Mammals	SD
CBH-035	77.5	12.1	5.3	3.8	12.1	10.8	5.2	3.7
CBH-013	70.5	10.5	5.4	3.7	18.7	9.9	5.3	4.0
CBH-01	70.0	9.7	6.6	4.2	15.9	9.0	7.5	4.7
CBH-033	67.4	11.1	7.0	4.7	8.5	6.0	17.1	8.4
CBH-019	66.3	11.6	5.6	4.2	22.5	10.5	5.6	4.6
CBH-06	65.8	18.0	9.0	7.3	13.2	11.7	12.0	8.9
CBH-015	59.3	12.4	9.0	5.8	21.5	11.0	10.2	6.5
CBH-05	59.3	12.2	7.2	5.2	26.5	11.3	7.0	5.2
CBH-032	58.5	21.4	10.9	8.7	17.4	15.9	13.3	9.6
CBH-028	57.1	9.0	5.7	3.6	31.9	9.1	5.3	3.1
CBH-026	55.8	8.9	5.4	3.5	34.2	9.1	4.6	2.7
CBH-011	55.5	11.4	8.3	5.1	28.2	11.2	8.0	4.6
CBH-04	54.3	21.0	11.3	9.0	15.8	13.7	18.6	12.7
CBH-021	53.7	10.1	9.3	5.4	27.2	9.9	9.8	4.9
CBH-014	52.7	8.2	9.5	5.5	25.3	8.3	12.5	5.0
CBH-018	52.4	8.8	10.6	6.2	19.3	8.4	17.8	6.2
CBH-025	49.7	17.9	11.7	8.8	27.2	15.6	11.4	8.2
CBH-016	49.5	9.8	10.7	6.1	28.8	9.7	11.1	5.2
CBH-037	48.6	14.7	8.7	7.9	36.0	13.1	6.7	5.2
CBH-024	48.4	11.1	8.4	5.1	36.5	10.8	6.6	3.8
CBH-029	48.1	17.7	13.2	8.9	23.9	14.2	14.9	10.3
CBH-031	47.1	12.6	8.5	7.9	37.5	10.5	6.8	5.4
CBH-023	46.7	9.4	8.2	4.8	39.1	9.4	5.9	3.2
CBH-034	46.3	18.2	10.3	9	35.7	16.7	7.6	5.8
CBH-012	41.0	12.6	14.3	9.4	30.5	10.5	14.2	7.0
CBH-07	31.6	9.5	19.3	9.5	18.8	9.1	30.3	7.5
CBH-09	26.9	14.1	20.6	15.0	17.3	11.5	35.2	15.8
CBH-027	10.0	3.7	58.1	5.4	14.5	4.7	17.3	3.1
CBH-017	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
CBH-020	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
CBH-030	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
CBH-036	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

Table S6. Capture dates, sex, months of monitoring, number of locations, and annual MCP home range estimates (km²) for resident coyotes fitted with GPS radiocollars in Cape Breton Highlands National Park. MCP not estimated because of brevity of monitoring period (ID 13, 21) or coyote was a transient during monitoring period (CBH-25).

ID	Capture Date	Sex	Months	Locations (n)	MCP
CBH-01	10/27/2011	M	8	1022	134
CBH-03	10/30/2011	M	8	1466	87
CBH-05	11/12/2011	M	8	1525	42
CBH-06	11/19/2011	M	10	2005	33
CBH-07	06/ 26/2012	M	3	911	13
CBH-08	07/18/2012	M	11	1478	124
CBH-11	10/14/2012	F	5	1207	79
CBH-13	10/ 15/2012	F	1	305	–
CBH-18	11/10/2012	M	9	492	78
CBH-19	05/06/2013	M	6	1031	108
CBH-21	06/23/2013	M	1	138	–
CBH-23	07/01/2013	M	6	1210	130
CBH-25	11/13/2013	M	6	1031	–
CBH-26	11/15/2013	M	10	4129	23

Table S7. P-values of posthoc Tukey-Kramer HSD pairwise comparisons of potential prey isotope values based on one-way ANOVAs of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ($F_{3,124} = 35.1$, $P < 0.001$) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ ($F_{3,124} = 47.0$, $P < 0.001$) values. Numbers above the dashes (upper right) are p-values for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data, numbers below (lower left) are p-values for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ data.

	Small Mammals	Deer	Moose	Snowshoe Hare
Small Mammals	–	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.002
Deer	0.0013	–	0.061	0.016
Moose	<0.0001	<0.0001	–	0.891
Snowshoe Hare	<0.0001	0.002	0.673	–

Table S8. Results of small mammal trapping conducted in Cape Breton Highlands National Park in 2012 and 2013; total trap nights (TTN), total captures, and capture rate (captures/100 trap nights). Arrays of 20 traps were set for 3-6 nights per site.

Location		Live Trap			Snap Trap		
		TTN	Captures	Capture Rate	TTN	Captures	Capture Rate
North Mountain	Plateau	80	1	1.3	100	3	3.0
French Mountain	Plateau	80	11	13.8	60	2	3.3
Fall Back Lake	Plateau	240	50	20.8	–	–	–
Forest	Lowland	80	41	51.3	60	21	35.0
Cheticamp	Lowland	80	33	41.3	–	–	–

Figure S1. Provincial pellet group inventory results for Victoria and Inverness Counties in Nova Scotia for (A) ungulates and (B) snowshoe hare provided by Nova Scotia Department of Lands and Forestry.

Figure S2. Relationships between intraindividual variability in diet, measured as the intra-vibrissa standard deviation, and mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (A) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (B) values for coyotes at Cape Breton Highlands National Park, Nova Scotia. Individual coyotes associated with attacks on people (blue circles) or had isotope values that indicated they consumed human foods (black circles) are labeled.

Appendix S1 (Summary of Fatal Incident). At approximately 3:15 pm on October 27, 2009, a 19-year-old female Taylor Mitchell was fatally wounded on the Skyline Trail in Cape Breton Highlands National Park (CBHNP). The nature of the Mitchell incident was such that it appeared that coyotes were responsible for attacking the victim, making it the first recorded case of an adult human killed by coyotes. One of the authors (EMM) was a responder to the scene of the incident and another author (SDG) conducted extensive interviews in 2010 of individuals (e.g., hikers, emergency responders, veterinary pathologists, CBHNP personnel) involved in different aspects of the incident. Below are relevant facts known about the case:

A) There is no evidence that the victim was injured, or behaving in a way to attract predators, or otherwise may have instigated an attack. The victim was a healthy physically fit adult female hiking alone on the Skyline Trail in CBHNP. There was no evidence that she was carrying food, or any other attractants for coyotes. She was dressed for a hike in cold weather. A pair of hikers encountered her on the trail before the attack and did not notice anything unusual about her.

B) The coyotes were healthy and acting boldly toward people that day, which is consistent with a predation event. The coyotes were acting extremely bold toward humans prior to the attack. Minutes prior to the attack, a pair of hikers on the trail encountered at least 2 coyotes exhibiting extremely bold behavior and unafraid of the hikers. The hikers were fearful of the coyotes and backed off the trail to let the coyotes pass. There were no other known hikers on the trail at this time.

C) There was no evidence of food provisioning as a cause of the attack and no previous reports of bold coyote behavior. There had not been reports of bold coyotes on the trail in the weeks or months prior to the attack. The pair of hikers mentioned above had hiked the Skyline Trail each week throughout much of the summer and fall and had not seen coyotes on the trail prior to this incident.

D) Coyotes were confirmed to be responsible for the attack, and their behavior at the site was consistent with a predation event, as was the injuries to the victim. Coyotes were directly linked to the attack and injuries were consistent with predation. There were no witnesses to the initial stages of the attack. A subsequent group of hikers discovered the victim on the ground, incapacitated, and guarded by at least two coyotes. Although semi-conscious, her wounds were extensive and consistent with predation. Coyotes continued to threaten the hikers while they attended to the victim. The victim soon lost consciousness and died later in the evening from her injuries.

E) Coyotes associated with the attack and others removed from the site were healthy and in typical condition, which is consistent with a predation event. Coyotes associated with the attack were healthy. Coyotes removed at the scene and in the following days (n=7) were necropsied at the Atlantic Veterinary College, University of Prince Edward Island, and found to be healthy with no evidence of abnormal physical limitations or disease.

Appendix S2 (Provincial Coyote Bounties). The fatal coyote attack at CBHNP in 2009 was the primary stimulus for initiating a Provincial coyote bounty during 2010–2015. These bounties were the subject of several articles in provincial and national media, including but not limited to:

- MacDonald, M. April 22, 2010. N.S. expected to offer trappers new bounty for coyotes. Cape Breton Post. “Glavine said the province has been under pressure to act since the mauling death last fall of a Toronto woman who was hiking in Cape Breton.”
- McGregor P. November 12, 2015. Coyote trapping incentive program ends in Nova Scotia. But did it work? CBC News. <https://www.cbc.ca/news/canada/nova-scotia/coyote-pelt-incentive-program-1.3315522> “The five-year program, which has now wrapped up, was launched in response to the death of Taylor Mitchell, the Toronto folk singer who died after being attacked by coyotes in Cape Breton Highlands National Park in 2009.”
- Anonymous. February 12, 2010. Coyotes coming closer to New Brunswick communities. CBC.
- Anonymous. January 27, 2010. Coyote bounties considered in parts of Ontario. <https://www.farms.com/farmspages/commentary/detailedcommentary/tabid/192/default.aspx?newsid=27481>
- Anonymous. May 27, 2010. Saskatchewan minister defends coyote bounty. CTV News.
- Talaga T. March 3, 2011. Shoot a coyote, win a prize: Ontario considers ‘contest’. Toronto Star.

Appendix S3 (Study Area). Our fieldwork was focused in and along the edges of CBHNP, which is a 948 km² park situated at the north end of Cape Breton Island, Nova Scotia (46°43’0”N, 60°39’35”W). The park is bounded to the east by the Cabot Strait and to the west by the Gulf of Saint Lawrence. Sharp increases in topography characterize the boundaries and canyons of the park, topped by a high central plateau with taiga and boreal vegetation, while deciduous forest habitat characterizes the lowlands. The location between two bodies of water, temperate latitude, and the altitude of the highland plateau results in a unique climate in and around the park. The plateau is considered a distinct climatic region in Nova Scotia, with a shorter growing season, longer periods of snow cover, greater daily temperature extremes, and more precipitation than the lowlands. The coastal areas and Cape Breton Highlands experience the highest mean annual wind speeds in the province (Keys et al. 2017), including regularly sustained winds of 10-50 km/hr, and occasionally windstorms of greater magnitudes between 50-100 km/hr (ECCC 2021). Winters are long and typically extend from November through April. The extreme climatic condition on the plateau, particularly the wind, is reflected in a dense, short, scrubby spruce forest relative to lowland areas (Taylor et al. 2020).

White-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) used to be abundant within the park but declined during the 1980’s (Fig. S1) and now are patchily distributed within the lowlands. Snowshoe hare (*Lepus americanus*) populations typically cycle but were rare during our fieldwork (Fig. S1). Moose (*Alces americanus*) are the most common ungulates in the park and were abundant during the study with an estimated population density of 2.24/km² in 2011 (CBHNP, unpublished data). Coyotes are not native to Nova Scotia and arrived on the island by 1980 (Parker 1995). In addition to coyotes, other predators in the park include Canadian lynx (*Lynx canadensis*), bobcat (*Lynx rufus*), and black bear (*Ursus americanus*).

Cabot Trail, a single 2–3 lane road, traverses three sides of the perimeter of the park and connects the few human communities adjacent to CBHNP (Fig. 1). Small local towns along the park boundary include Cheticamp

(population size ~3,000), Ingonish (population size ~1,900), and Pleasant Bay (population size ~250) (2006 Census). Visitation to the park is typically 150,000 annually, with most park use taking place from June to October (Parks Canada 2010). Human activity in the park is focused in picnic areas, hiking trails, and camp sites, which are accessed from the Cabot Trail. Thus, human activity tends to be concentrated along the perimeter road regardless of the type of activity, with low local human densities outside the park and little human presence in the interior.

Appendix S4 (Live-Trapping and Tracking). We live-captured coyotes opportunistically throughout the year during 2011–2013 using foothold traps and cable restraints. We did not trap during extreme winter conditions. When a coyote was captured, we immobilized it with an injection of Telazol and recorded age, sex, body weight, and various body measurements. We collected two whiskers with scissors from the posterior portion of the muzzle. A subsample of coyotes >12 kg body weight were fitted with Lotek 7000 GPS collars (Lotek Wireless Inc., Newmarket, Ontario, Canada) with remote communication, or GSC Pinnacle LITE GPS Iridium collars (Sirtrack, New Zealand). Other coyotes were fitted with VHF radiocollars (Advanced Telemetry Systems, Isanti, Minnesota, USA). All coyotes were released at the capture site, typically within a few hours following immobilization. Animal capture and handling was conducted in accordance with Parks Canada Research Permit 12020, which was approved by Parks Canada's Animal Care Committee.

We attempted to systematically distribute GPS collars to reduce non-independence and to expand our sampling across the park. Trapping efforts were clustered at different points of the park and if an adult was captured it was fitted with a GPS collar; other coyotes captured near trapping clusters were fitted with a VHF collar with the goal of applying a GPS collar to only one member of each pack or social group.

Relocation schedules for GPS transmitters were programmed for a location every 2 hours for the first 8 weeks post-deployment, then 6 or 7 hours for the remainder of the transmitter schedule. Relocation schedules also included locations separated by 2-hour intervals during 24-hour intermittent shifts each month. Data were downloaded remotely on an opportunistic basis when animals were in suitable locations. Occasionally, it was necessary to fly fixed-wing aircraft to download data for coyotes located on the central plateau with no terrestrial access. Data from iridium collars were automatically uploaded to a data cloud.

SI References

- Aebischer, M., Robertson, P.A., & Kenward, R.E. (1993). Compositional analysis of habitat use from animal radio-tracking data. *Ecology* 74:1313–1325.
- Beyer, H.L. (2012). Geospatial Modelling Environment (Version 0.7.2.1). (software).
- Calenge, C. (2006). The package "adehabitat" for the R software: A tool for the analysis of space and habitat use by animals. *Ecological Modelling* 197:516–519.
- Ellington, E.H., Muntz, E.M., & Gehrt, S.D. (2020). Seasonal and daily shifts in behavior and resource selection: how a carnivore navigates costly landscapes. *Oecologia* 194:87–100.
- Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) (2021). Canadian climate normals 1981-2010. Environment and climate change Canada. Available from:
https://climate.weather.gc.ca/climate_normals/results_1981_2010_e.html?searchType=stnProv&lstProvince=NS&txtCentralLatMin=0&txtCentralLatSec=0&txtCentralLongMin=0&txtCentralLongSec=0&stnID=6358&dispBack=0
- Johnson, D. (1980). The comparison of usage and availability measurements for evaluating resource preferences. *Ecology* 61:65–71.
- Keys, K., Garron, E., Oikle, D., Quigley, E., Neily, P., McGrath, T., et al. (2017). Digital wind exposure map for Nova Scotia. Nova Scotia Department of Lands and Forestry, Halifax, N.S., Report FOR 2017-15.
- Lowe, S.J., Patterson, B.R., & Schaefer, J.A. (2010). Lack of behavioral responses of moose (*Alces alces*) to high ambient temperatures near the southern periphery of their range. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 88:1032–1041.
- Parker, G.R. (1995). Eastern coyote: the story of its success. Nimbus Publishing Ltd., Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada.
- Parks Canada (2010) Cape Breton Highlands National Park of Canada Management Plan, Parks Canada, 70 pp.
- Patterson, B.R., Bondrup-Nielsen, S., & Messier, F. (1999). Activity patterns and daily movements of the eastern coyote *Canis latrans* in Nova Scotia. *Canadian Field Naturalist* 113:251–257.
- R Core Team (2015) R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <http://www.R-project.org/>
- Rhoads, C.L., Bowman, J.L., & Eyler, B. (2010). Home range and movement rates of female exurban white-tailed deer. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 74:987–994.
- Taylor, A.R., MacLean, D.A., Neily, P.D., et al. (2020). A review of natural disturbances to inform implementation of ecological forestry in Nova Scotia, Canada. *Environmental Review* 28:387-414.